

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B356
Date: 10 April 2008
Take Off: 10:43:20Z
Landing: 15:42:24Z
Flight Time 4h 59

Campaign: ADIENT

Operating Area: East coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Megan Northway	University of Reading
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist2	Steve Abel	Met Office
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office
10	Wet Neph	Andy Wilson	Met Office
11	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
12	SP2	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester

Flight Track:

B356 Track 10-APR-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B356
 Date: 10 April 2008
 Project: ADIENT
 Location: East Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
083730		Start-Up	0.75 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
103517		ASP	0.76 kft	070	Open
104320		T/O	1.9 kft	276	Cranfield
104839		Video	7.0 kft	053	Start FFC & UFC
104933		Event	7.0 kft	057	Zero JW & Nevz
110954	111729	Profile 1	11.0 - 3.5 kft	180	To 3k' on QNH 996, 1k'fpm
111739	112422	Profile 1	3.4 - 0.42 kft	184	3k-50', 500fpm, Q999
112517	113445	Run 1.1	0.86 - 0.90 kft	195	500', WP40-WP42
113028		Event	0.92 kft	194	Heimann cal
113556	125304	Run 1.2	0.84 - 1.0 kft	010	500', From WP42
114913		Event	0.90 kft	012	WP41
115656		Event	0.95 kft	007	Zero Nevz LWC
120434		Event	0.93 kft	357	WP40
122344		Video	0.92 kft	324	Change Tapes
124257		Event	0.95 kft	327	QNH 997
124818		Event	0.98 kft	327	Heimann cal
125345		Event	0.99 kft	065	Turn to avoid rain
125444	130119	Profile 2	0.92 - 4.5 kft	159	500'-4k', 500fpm
130119	131127	Run 2	4.5 kft	158	4k'
131128	131816	Profile 3	4.5 - 0.94 kft	150	4k- 500', 500fpm
131827	132813	Run 3.1	0.94 - 0.90 kft	154	500'
132929	133700	Run 3.2	0.98 - 0.96 kft	335	500'
133323		Event	0.94 kft	324	Heimann cal
133836	133954	Orbit 1	0.98 - 1.0 kft	111	45deg left bank, start 100deg
134027	134143	Orbit 2	1.00 - 1.0 kft	059	45deg left bank, start 060deg
134253	134913	Run 3.3	0.97 - 0.93 kft	168	500'
135049	135640	Profile 4	0.97 - 4.5 kft	322	500-4k', 500fpm
135706		Video	4.5 kft	007	Change tapes
135925	140041	Orbit 3	4.4 kft	150	45deg left bank, start 140deg
140114	140231	Orbit 4	4.5 kft	107	45deg left bank, start 080deg
140309	141309	Run 4.1	4.5 kft	124	4k'
141449	142452	Run 5	4.0 kft	301	Descend to FL40 for ATC
142631	143459	Profile 5	4.0 - 0.46 kft	142	To 50', 500fpm, Q997
143557	143644	Run 6.1	0.90 - 0.93 kft	152	500' - Abort run
143654	143923	Profile 6.1	0.96 - 2.4 kft	148	Sawtooth 500'-2k'
143923	144159	Profile 6.2	2.4 - 0.93 kft	152	2k-500', 500fpm
144159	144457	Profile 6.3	0.93 - 2.5 kft	148	500-2k', 500fpm
144620	145011	Profile 7	2.5 - 0.93 kft	330	2k-500', 500fpm
145011	150011	Run 7	0.90 - 0.93 kft	325	500'
145159		Event	0.96 kft	328	QNH 998
150114	150727	Profile 8	0.98 - 4.0 kft	166	From 500', 500fpm
150926	151517	Profile 8	4.0 - 10.0 kft	186	
151119		Event	6.0 kft	185	Sonde sighted
152549		ASP	4.6 kft	265	Close
154224		Land	0.81 kft	330	Cranfield 154224
154606		Shutdown	0.81 kft	313	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B356 Track 10-APR-08

FAAM Sortie Debrief

Flight Number B356 ADIENT

Thursday April 10, 2008

Mission Scientist - Megan Northway

Sortie Objectives: To identify and characterize aerosol plumes and optical properties with a combination of in situ and radiation measurements. Mission critical instruments: PCASP, wet nephelometer, ToF-AMS

Operating Area: UK operating areas D and E

Weather: West/SW winds were predicted to advect some aerosol plumes off the E. coast of the UK, particularly off Weybourne and Teeside. High aerosol loadings and clear skies expected for radiation work. Patches of clear skies were observed but some persistent contrails and low level stratus were also observed. This will have to be filtered carefully for the analysis.

Flight Patterns: Take-off from Cranfield at 10:45Z was approximately 1 hour late because of problems with HORACE. Strat-cume cloud ceiling was around 5000ft. A brown haze layer was visible on the horizon once above the aerosol. A profile descent was performed starting at waypoint 40 off Norwich from FL110, and ending at 50 ft near waypoint 41. A 500 ft run was commenced heading south through the channel towards waypoint 42. Skies were clear above this track. After reaching point 42, the 500 ft run was reversed up the E. coast and strat-cume cloud was increasingly dense above until rain was encountered near Teeside before reaching waypoint 77. After a turn to the south, a sawtooth profile was commenced to 4000 ft followed by a run at 4000 ft. Given that skies were relatively clear over this track, the area between waypoints 79 and 80 was chosen to complete some radiation work. This composed of two straight and level runs at 500 ft and 4500 ft with 2 x 2 orbits completed at the end of each run. After the last run, a profile to 50 ft was performed followed by two sawtooth profiles from 500 to 2000 ft through the aerosol plume. These were extended further out from the coast, still remaining in the clear skies. A final run was commenced at 500 ft followed by a profile climb through the aerosol plume up to FL100 for the transit home.

Summary: A good flight for surveying aerosol levels on the east coast in westerly conditions. Some radiation work was carried out, but will have to be analyzed carefully for cloud.

Instrument Problems: No problems to note.

Aerosol

At 13Z on 10/ 4/2008, from 03Z on 10/ 4/2008

1 2 5 7 10 15 20 25 30 50 100

At 13Z on 10/ 4/2008, from 03Z on 10/ 4/2008
Cloud cover and PMSL Operational uk4

High > 50%
Med > 50%
Low > 50%
Stratus > 10%
Fog > 40%

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page ...!.....

Flight No **B.356** Date **10 Apr** Name **Megan Northway** Page **1** of **4**

Local
1 hr

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					T/O Ground conditions 1/8 scattered cu
~9:50					Problem w/ horace - rebooting
					cameras default setting forward + upward
					Late T/O b/c of Horace problems
					pirouette scrubbed - cloud now 2/8-3/8
					wind 210 9 knots
~10:45					T/O
~10:46					cloud ceiling about 3000 ft - 5000ft
~10:48		7000ft			just at cloud top level
11:09:54	P1	F110			P1 descent commencing
11:14	P1	8400			thick stratus - cloud base
11:14	P1	6300			1 ug/m ³ NO ₃ ams
11:18		3000			brown haze layer visible below
11:21	P1	2000			NO _x , Ams call seeing high pollution 1.7 ug/m ³ NO ₃
					scat peaked at
11:24:22		50ft			end of P1
11:25:17		500ft			start of R1.1
11:27	R1	"			clear skies above
11:34	R1	"			passing white cliffs of Dover
11:35					clear skies again - end of R1.1
					way point 42
					Turning to head back U. sup coast
11:35:56	R1.2	500ft			start of run

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page 2

Flight No **B.356** Date 10 Apr 2008 Name Megan Norstrom Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:39	R1.2	subft			Stratus above again
					wide plumes in ^{SO₂} NO _x - very variable
11:48	"	"			several $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NO ₃ - AMS
					clear skies above
11:49	"	"			passing waypoint 41
					main plume 51.7 N
12:04	"	"			Dave sent a satellite photo of cloud coverage - very much confined to coast - moving away from coast on track to waypoint 40
12:05					passing waypoint 40
12:23	"	"			neph + chemistry peak
12:43	"	"			more plumes - agrees w/ model (aerosol)
					sustained wind
12:50	"	"			coming into some cloud above heading to 77 then turning around
12:54	"	"			rain ahead - came up quickly turning around
12:55:00	P2				profile to 4000 ft
					- some cloud around - but not
					1/8 a
13:02:00	R2	2400ft			end of P2 - Run at 400 ft
13:13:00	R2				some aerosol + plumes up here
13:13:00	P3				profile to 500 ft
13:28	1				hit cloud - turning N again

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page 4.....

Flight No **B**356 Date 10 Apr 2008 Name Melissa Northing Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:45	P6.3	500 - 2000ft			end of P6
		2000ft			turn to NW
14:46:20	P7				profile descent to 500 500 ft
14:50	R7	500ft			final reciprocal run at 500 ft
15:01	R7				end of R7
Start of 15:01:15	P8	500ft - 2000 10000			profile climb to FL100
					cloud ceiling
15:03	P8				cloud at above nar big stratus above 5000
15:	P8				cloud ceiling

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page 3.....

Flight No B.356 Date 10 Apr 2008 Name Mogam Narayana Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:29:29	3.2	500ft			clear skies above - backtracking reciprocal run. only 7.5 min block of airspace
13:37	3.2	500ft			2x 45° Bank angle - end of Run orbits (fighter jet 9 o'clock)
13:38	3.2				turn to S track
13:39-		500ft			2x 45° Bank angle left orbits
13:42	end of orbits	500ft			no cloud in front of sun, but $\approx 1/8$ Cn/ci around
13:45	3.3	500ft			reciprocal track
13:49:14					end of 3.3
	P4	to 4000ft			up to 4000ft
13:56:48	P4	"			end of P4
13:59					looking for clear space ^{above} for orbit
13:52:25				orbit 3 " 4	2x 45° Bank angle
14:02:31					end of orbit 4
14:14	R4.1	4000ft			
14:14:49	R5	4000ft			reciprocal run
14:17	R5	"			cloud coming in on all sides (still clear above)
14:24:52	R5	"			run 5 end
14:28-	P5	P5 to 50ft			profile to 50ft
14:31	"	"			-1500ft coming back into area
14:34:59					end of P5
14:39:00					saw toothing 2500-2000ft

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B356

Date:

10/04/2008

Processing completed by: Phil Brown

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B356_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B356_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B356 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B356_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B356 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc'] Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B356_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B356_mfdX','pmsdata:B356_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B356_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B356_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly		

synchronized in time?		
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B356**Date:**

10/04/2008

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B356.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B356.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B356.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B356.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B356_seadas.dat iii) exit	16/04/2008	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 0 bad reads
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B356 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B356_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	16/04/2008	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Not required Not required
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' j) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B356 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Preparation of imagery for Core data product		

iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B356 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	104300 154300 10	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B356_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	16/04/08	
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: B356 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B356_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B356_PROC2D	0 104300 154300 0.2 8/8 2 16/04/08	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B356_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B356_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	16/04/08	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B356_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B356_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	16/04/08	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		Unable to compare

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B356**Date:**

10/04/2008

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B356_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: B356 b) File name: PMSDATA:B356_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B356_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B356_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B356_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	0.75 cm ³ /s 0 104300 154300	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B356_procpcasp.dat' , 'pmsdata:B356_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	16/04/08	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B356_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:B356_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	16/04/08	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B356**Date:**

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E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B356_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B356.nc]	16/04/08	As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B356.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B356.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B356_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	16/04/08	

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B356*.* outdir:B356_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	16/04/08	Note destination directory "outdir" CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B356**Date:**

10/04/2008

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B356_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B356_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B356_FFSSP.raw B356_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B356_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B356.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B356.zip) - rename B356.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B356_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B356_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B356_rawseadas.zip	16/04/08	Binary data transfer

B356_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

08:28:42.63 --- - - - -
08:28:42.63 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:28:42.63 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:28:42.64 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B356
08:28:42.64 --- - - - -
08:29:20.66 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:29:29.31 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
08:29:30.42 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:29:44.38 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:29:48.08 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:29:50.22 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:31:24.26 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:33:07.00 --- - - - - *** B356 ADIENT in North Sea
08:33:21.44 --- - - - - *** Operator Martin Glew
08:34:09.11 --- - - - - *** All Modules Working pre-take off
08:34:27.58 --- - - - - *** SWS telescope windows cleaned
08:51:13.06 --- - - - -
08:51:13.06 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:51:13.06 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:51:13.06 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B356
08:51:13.06 --- - - - -
08:51:17.89 SWS - - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
08:51:24.75 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:51:26.93 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:52:16.01 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
08:52:25.38 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 50.0
08:52:43.13 SWS 49.9 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:53:00.86 SWS -54.9 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 50.0
08:53:18.62 SWS 49.9 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:53:28.40 SWS -6.6 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:53:39.73 SWS -6.5 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
08:53:40.84 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:53:46.33 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:53:47.44 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:53:50.51 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:53:52.17 SWS 169.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:54:04.03 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
08:54:05.15 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:56:53.36 --- - - - -
08:56:53.36 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:56:53.36 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:56:53.36 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B356
08:56:53.36 --- - - - -
08:57:10.84 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:57:54.39 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -52.000
08:57:57.45 SWS -17.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:58:04.36 SWS -17.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
08:58:05.47 SWS 89.5 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:58:51.60 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:58:55.47 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:58:58.98 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:59:27.97 --- - - - - *** Cooler 0 deg C
08:59:40.94 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:59:44.81 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:59:47.41 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:59:51.65 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:59:55.01 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:59:57.59 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:00:02.15 SWS - - 1000 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
09:00:02.16 SWS - - - 1000 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
09:00:08.80 USH - - 1000 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
09:00:08.81 USH - - - 1000 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
09:00:13.54 LSH - - 1000 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
09:00:13.54 LSH - - - 1000 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.

```

```

09:00:16.33 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:00:20.28 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:00:24.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:24.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:24.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:35.39 USH - - - - Idling
09:00:35.64 LSH - - - - Idling
09:00:36.12 SWS - - - - Idling
09:00:37.32 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:37.32 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:37.33 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:00:47.76 SWS - - - - Idling
09:00:47.97 LSH - - - - Idling
09:00:48.16 USH - - - - Idling
09:00:51.23 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:00:51.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:00:51.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:00.55 USH - - - - Idling
09:01:00.76 LSH - - - - Idling
09:01:00.95 SWS - - - - Idling
09:01:07.03 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:01:07.03 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:01:11.55 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:01:11.55 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:01:14.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:01:14.91 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:01:14.91 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:01:17.19 SWS - - - - Idling
09:01:17.33 USH - - - - Idling
09:01:23.26 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:01:24.71 SWS - - - - Idling
09:01:24.77 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:01:25.82 LSH - - - - Idling
09:01:26.22 USH - - - - Idling
09:01:30.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:30.01 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:30.02 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:38.71 USH - - - - Idling
09:01:38.93 SWS - - - - Idling
09:01:39.55 LSH - - - - Idling
09:01:40.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:40.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:40.61 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:45.71 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:01:51.57 SWS - - - - Idling
09:01:51.77 USH - - - - Idling
09:01:52.97 LSH - - - - Idling
09:01:54.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:54.02 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:01:54.02 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:02:11.41 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
09:02:12.52 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:02:22.76 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
09:02:23.87 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:03:12.04 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:03:22.49 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:04:36.61 --- - - - - *** Cooler temp +4 deg C
09:06:48.05 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -52.000
09:06:49.71 SWS -52.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:07:08.05 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -52.0
09:07:26.39 SWS -52.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:07:36.20 SWS 4.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:07:40.03 SWS - - 5 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 5ms.
09:07:40.04 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 5ms.
09:07:44.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:07:44.51 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:07:46.47 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:07:46.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:07:47.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

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09:07:47.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:47.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:07:49.04	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:07:51.24	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 10ms.
09:07:55.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:55.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:07:55.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:07:56.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:07:58.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:08:03.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:08:05.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:08:08.14	SWS	4.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -52.000
09:08:18.09	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:08:36.46	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -52.0
09:08:54.81	SWS	-52.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:09:13.18	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -52.0
09:09:21.88	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:09:42.08	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -46.000
09:09:50.94	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:10:06.06	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 15ms.
09:10:08.23	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:10:08.67	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 15ms.
09:10:09.64	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 15ms to 15ms.
09:10:12.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:12.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:10:12.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:17.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:17.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:25.51	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:10:32.35	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
09:10:32.35	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
09:10:34.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:34.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:10:35.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:36.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:10:37.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:10:42.76	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:11:00.00	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:11:17.27	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:11:34.53	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:11:51.79	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:12:09.05	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:12:26.30	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:12:43.58	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:13:00.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:13:18.10	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:13:35.36	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:13:52.63	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:14:09.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:14:27.16	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:14:44.43	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:15:01.70	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:15:18.96	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:15:36.23	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:15:53.52	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:16:10.78	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:16:28.04	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:16:45.32	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:17:02.60	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:17:19.84	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:17:37.11	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:17:54.40	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:18:11.67	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:18:28.96	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:18:46.25	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:19:03.52	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:19:20.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:19:38.10	SWS	-46.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:19:55.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0

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09:20:12.68 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:20:29.97 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:20:47.26 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:21:04.55 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:21:21.83 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:21:39.13 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:21:56.43 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:22:13.73 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:22:31.05 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:22:48.37 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:23:05.65 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:23:22.96 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:23:40.28 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:23:57.60 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:24:14.92 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:24:32.23 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:24:49.54 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:25:06.86 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:25:24.19 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:25:41.52 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:25:58.95 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:26:16.26 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:26:33.54 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:26:50.64 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:27:07.99 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:27:25.33 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:27:42.70 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:28:00.03 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:28:17.40 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:28:34.79 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:28:52.17 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:29:09.53 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -46.0
09:29:26.89 SWS -46.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:29:40.66 SWS 34.5 - - - Telescope stopped.
09:29:40.97 SWS 34.5 - - - Telescope sent to -46.000
09:29:42.39 SWS 27.3 - - - Telescope stopped.
09:29:50.12 SWS 27.3 - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
09:29:51.24 SWS 90.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
09:34:35.85 --- - - - *** Cooler temp +2 deg C
09:35:26.78 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:35:26.78 USH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:35:53.44 USH - - - Idling
09:35:53.56 LSH - - - Idling
09:35:53.75 SWS - - - Idling
09:35:55.46 --- - - - Reset shutters.
09:36:02.57 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:02.57 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:02.58 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:03.52 SWS - - - Idling
09:36:05.42 USH - - - Idling
09:36:06.25 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:06.25 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:07.20 SWS - - - Idling
09:36:08.90 USH - - - Idling
09:36:09.45 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:09.45 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:10.40 SWS - - - Idling
09:36:12.09 USH - - - Idling
09:36:12.80 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:12.80 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:13.21 LSH - - - Idling
09:36:13.95 SWS - - - Idling
09:36:15.26 USH - - - Idling
09:36:17.32 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:17.33 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:17.33 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:18.27 SWS - - - Idling
09:36:20.17 USH - - - Idling
09:36:22.01 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
```

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09:36:22.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:36:23.16 SWS - - - - Idling
09:36:24.46 USH - - - - Idling
09:36:27.97 LSH - - - - Idling
09:36:32.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:36:37.74 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:36:42.27 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:36:44.68 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:49:59.64 --- - - - - ***
09:51:25.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:26.08 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:26.19 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:27.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:51:28.31 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:31.66 USH - - - - Idling
09:51:32.02 SWS - - - - Idling
09:51:34.20 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:36.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:36.65 USH - - - - Idling
09:51:37.19 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:37.19 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:37.77 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:38.34 SWS - - - - Idling
09:51:39.64 USH - - - - Idling
09:51:42.87 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:43.81 SWS - - - - Idling
09:51:44.33 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:51:46.81 USH - - - - Idling
09:51:48.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:51:48.77 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:51:48.79 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:51:49.46 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:54:41.23 --- - - - - *** Take off delayed, HORACE not working
09:55:57.86 --- - - - - *** Cooler temp +1 deg C
10:12:15.08 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:15.17 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:15.19 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:21.75 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:12:21.76 USH - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:12:28.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:28.81 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:28.82 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:29.08 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:12:30.00 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:12:30.18 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:30.23 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:12:31.13 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:37.58 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:12:39.46 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:43.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:43.26 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:43.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:44.21 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:45.11 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:47.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:47.25 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:48.21 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:48.91 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:49.64 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:49.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:50.60 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:51.30 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:53.92 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:56.24 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:56.24 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:56.25 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:27:18.20 --- - - - -
10:27:18.20 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++

```

```

10:27:18.20 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:27:18.20 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B356
10:27:18.20 --- - - - -
10:27:25.03 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
10:27:38.65 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
10:27:39.76 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
10:27:54.92 SWS - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:27:57.09 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:28:01.05 LSH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:28:02.29 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:28:04.18 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:28:06.45 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:28:15.48 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:29:14.53 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:29:25.50 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:29:35.30 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:29:41.45 USH - 1000 - - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
10:29:44.83 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:29:45.65 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:29:49.00 USH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:29:49.01 USH - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:29:52.66 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:30:01.16 LSH - - 1000 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
10:30:01.17 LSH - - - 1000 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 1000ms.
10:30:06.04 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:30:06.04 SWS - - - 50 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
10:30:08.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:30:08.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:30:08.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:30:10.35 SWS - - - - Idling
10:30:10.75 USH - - - - Idling
10:30:19.11 LSH - - - - Idling
10:31:00.96 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:00.97 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:00.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:01.90 SWS - - - - Idling
10:31:02.80 USH - - - - Idling
10:31:11.61 LSH - - - - Idling
10:31:14.59 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:14.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:14.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:15.53 SWS - - - - Idling
10:31:16.44 USH - - - - Idling
10:31:17.79 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:17.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:31:18.73 SWS - - - - Idling
10:31:19.42 USH - - - - Idling
10:31:25.24 LSH - - - - Idling
10:31:37.67 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:31:43.25 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:31:43.25 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:31:51.03 SWS - - - - Idling
10:31:51.06 LSH - - - - Idling
10:31:51.12 USH - - - - Idling
10:31:52.09 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:31:59.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:31:59.15 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:31:59.17 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:32:26.25 SWS - - - - Idling
10:32:26.51 USH - - - - Idling
10:32:26.96 LSH - - - - Idling
10:32:27.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:32:27.80 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:32:27.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:32:29.14 SWS - - - - Idling
10:32:29.24 USH - - - - Idling
10:32:38.43 LSH - - - - Idling
10:32:40.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

```

10:32:41.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:43.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:07.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +1 deg C
10:46:39.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:39.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:40.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:41.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:41.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:41.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:42.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:42.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:43.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:43.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:52.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:53.42	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:46:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:59.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:59.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:00.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:01.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:07.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:07.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:08.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:08.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:09.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:09.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:09.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:10.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:10.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:14.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:15.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:17.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:18.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:21.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:22.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:23.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:24.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:28.60	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:47:29.71	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:47:36.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:36.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:36.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:42.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:47:57.16	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:47:57.16	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:48:10.56	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
10:48:10.56	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
10:48:16.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:16.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:17.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:18.44	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:48:21.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:21.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:21.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:22.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:23.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:25.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:25.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:26.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:26.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:27.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:28.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:28.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:28.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:01.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:01.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:02.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:09.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.

10:54:14.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:14.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:14.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:15.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:16.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:17.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:17.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:18.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:18.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:19.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:19.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:19.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:19.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:20.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:21.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:21.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:21.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:35.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:56:39.17	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
10:56:41.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:50.14	LSH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.
10:57:24.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +1 deg C
10:57:56.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:57:59.66	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:57:59.67	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:58:05.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:07.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:08.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:11.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:12.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:10.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:02:46.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:02:53.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:03:17.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:17.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:17.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:19.42	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:03:22.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:22.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:22.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:23.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:23.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:24.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:25.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:26.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:27.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:28.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:29.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:32.37	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
11:03:32.37	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
11:03:35.15	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
11:03:35.16	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
11:03:37.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:37.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:37.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:39.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:40.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:40.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:42.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:42.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:42.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:15.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:19.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:31.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:05:36.30	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 25ms.
11:05:36.31	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 25ms.
11:05:39.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:40.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

11:05:43.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:44.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:05:47.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:54.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:54.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:54.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:59.58	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:09:03.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:03.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:03.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:04.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:05.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:06.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:08.54	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
11:09:12.28	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
11:09:16.37	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
11:09:25.45	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
11:09:25.46	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
11:09:38.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:38.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:40.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:40.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:41.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:43.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:43.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:43.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:43.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:10:42.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:12:30.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:12:36.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:38.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:12:41.97	LSH	-	-	1000	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 1000ms.
11:12:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	1000	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 1000ms.
11:12:46.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:12:56.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:12:58.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:08.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:10.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:22.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:23.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:25.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:13:26.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:44.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
11:13:44.48	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
11:13:46.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:49.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:51.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:52.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:32.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:32.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:32.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:34.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:14:38.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:40.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:40.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:43.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:44.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:48.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:51.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:33.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cloudy
11:20:07.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** Think in clear here
11:24:31.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:24:33.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:24:33.36	SWS	-3.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:24:35.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:37.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:24:41.17 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
11:24:41.18 SWS - - - 75 NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
11:24:43.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:24:45.09 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:25:10.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:25:12.08 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:25:15.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:25:26.03 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:29:33.28 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:29:44.02 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:29:45.29 --- - - - - *** patchy cloud
11:30:14.87 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:30:16.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:30:18.09 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:30:21.05 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
11:30:21.05 SWS - - - 30 NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
11:30:23.98 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:30:24.72 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:30:26.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:34:59.82 USH - - - - Idling
11:34:59.94 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:00.43 LSH - - - - Idling
11:35:01.49 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:35:07.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:07.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:07.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:08.70 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:09.78 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:11.04 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:11.04 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:12.01 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:12.50 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:15.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:15.04 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:15.84 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:16.69 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:17.16 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:17.17 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:17.92 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:18.58 LSH - - - - Idling
11:35:18.82 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:20.13 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:20.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:20.15 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:21.31 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:21.59 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:22.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:22.99 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:23.93 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:24.46 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:25.29 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:25.30 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:26.05 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:26.94 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:27.46 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:27.46 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:28.41 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:28.95 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:30.79 LSH - - - - Idling
11:35:33.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:35:33.30 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:35:33.31 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:37:59.31 --- - - - - *** cloudy
11:38:12.74 --- - - - - *** Cooler temp +1 deg C
11:44:05.64 --- - - - - *** Cloud free I think
11:44:22.83 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:44:23.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:44:28.91 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
11:44:28.92 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.

11:44:30.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:31.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:36.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:38.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:40.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:51.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:15.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:54:00.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloudy
11:54:05.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:07.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:10.50	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
11:54:10.50	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
11:54:12.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:13.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:22.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:22.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:22.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:23.55	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:54:27.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:27.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:27.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:28.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:29.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:32.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:32.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:33.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:33.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:36.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:36.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:37.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:37.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:54:39.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:39.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:39.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:26.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +1 deg C
12:04:47.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:47.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:48.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:49.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:04:54.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:54.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:54.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:55.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:56.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:56.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:56.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:57.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:58.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:58.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:58.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:59.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:00.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:00.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:00.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:01.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:02.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:05.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:05:06.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:06.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:06.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:00.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:00.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:01.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:02.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:18:07.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:07.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:07.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:07.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:18:09.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:17.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:24.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:24.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:24.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:26.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:26.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:27.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:27.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:28.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:29.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:29.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:29.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:30.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:31.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:31.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:31.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:33.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:35.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:18:36.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:36.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:36.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:50.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +1 deg C
12:21:09.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud free
12:21:26.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:21:28.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:29.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:21:33.25	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
12:21:33.25	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
12:21:35.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:36.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:21:38.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:39.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:21:42.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:45.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:47.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:50.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:00.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:25:18.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud patch
12:26:28.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** ...or it might be just aerosol
12:31:59.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:32:02.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:02.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:03.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:05.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:32:10.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:10.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:10.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:11.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:12.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:12.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:12.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:13.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:14.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:15.11	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
12:32:16.40	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
12:32:20.36	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:32:20.38	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:32:21.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:25.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:32:27.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:32.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:32.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:02.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +1 deg C
12:40:29.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:30.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:32.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:40:33.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
12:40:36.03	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
12:40:37.90	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:40:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:40:39.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:41.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:42.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:43.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:47.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:40:50.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:51.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:40:55.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:40:57.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:57.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:08.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:41:09.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:05.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** some cloud
12:51:18.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:18.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:19.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:20.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:51:24.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:24.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:24.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:26.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:27.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:27.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:28.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:28.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:29.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:29.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:30.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:30.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:31.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:31.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:32.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:33.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:33.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:33.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:34.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:34.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:35.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:35.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:35.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:35.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:43.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:51:48.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:51:53.60	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
12:51:53.61	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
12:51:55.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:56.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:51:57.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:08.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:08.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:09.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:21.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** rain ahead, run terminated
12:53:35.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coller temp +1 deg C
12:53:41.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:41.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:41.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:42.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:42.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:44.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:44.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:45.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:45.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:46.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:53:46.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:47.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:47.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:48.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:48.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:49.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:50.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:50.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:50.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:51.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:52.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:53.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:53.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:53.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:54.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:54.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:55.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:55.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:55.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:56.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:57.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:57.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:58.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:58.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:01.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:01.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:02.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:03.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:03.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:27.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:27.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:27.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:43.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:43.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:44.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:54:45.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:45.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:45.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:21.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:21.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:22.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:24.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:01:28.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:28.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:28.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:29.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:30.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:30.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:30.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:31.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:32.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:33.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:01:39.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:39.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:39.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:39.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:02.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:03.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:05.70	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
13:02:05.71	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
13:02:08.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:09.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:10.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:11.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:31.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:31.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:31.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:32.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:11:32.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:33.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:34.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:34.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:35.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:35.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:11:36.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:37.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:43.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:11:44.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:44.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:11:44.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:16.11	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:13:17.85	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:14:40.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:43.79	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
13:14:43.80	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
13:14:46.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:49.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:06.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloudy in profile
13:18:19.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:19.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:20.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:22.80	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:18:24.52	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:18:25.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:18:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:28.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:28.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:30.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:32.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:33.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:33.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:35.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:36.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:36.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:37.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:37.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:37.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:39.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:39.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:41.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:41.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:41.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:41.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:42.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:18:51.29	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 30ms.
13:18:51.30	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 30ms.
13:18:53.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:54.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:19:56.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:19:57.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:58.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:20:01.26	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
13:20:01.27	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
13:20:03.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:04.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:20:05.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:07.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:20:07.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:14.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:14.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:14.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:17.25	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:28:20.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:20.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:20.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:21.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:28:21.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:22.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:24.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:24.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:25.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:27.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:27.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:29.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:29.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:29.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:29.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:31.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:31.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:31.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:28:32.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:32.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:32.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:35.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:35.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:35.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:38.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:38.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:40.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:29:46.31	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:29:48.05	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:29:50.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:00.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:30:04.31	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
13:30:04.32	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
13:30:06.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:30:12.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:58.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:03.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:09.36	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 30ms.
13:35:09.37	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 30ms.
13:35:11.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:57.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:58.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:01.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:01.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:01.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:03.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:03.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:03.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:10.82	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 400ms.
13:36:10.83	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 400ms.
13:36:12.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:17.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:03.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:37:05.03	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:37:06.76	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:37:13.73	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 20ms.
13:37:13.74	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 20ms.
13:37:16.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:38:10.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:11.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:12.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:10.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:39:59.48	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
13:39:59.49	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
13:40:01.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:02.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:45.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:45.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:41:46.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:48.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:41:52.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:52.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:52.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:53.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:54.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:56.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:56.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:56.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:57.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:59.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:59.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:59.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:00.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:01.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:01.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:02.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:03.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:03.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:10.49	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
13:42:10.49	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
13:42:14.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:14.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:14.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:16.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:16.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:16.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:17.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:18.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:19.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:21.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:21.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:25.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:31.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:31.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:31.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:39.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:42:44.53	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:42:44.54	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:42:47.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:48.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:42:49.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:06.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +2 deg C
13:47:33.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:36.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:39.31	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
13:47:39.33	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
13:47:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:43.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:44.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:47.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:48.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:15.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:15.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:15.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:18.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:18.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:18.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:20.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:20.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:21.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:23.05	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:49:26.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:26.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:26.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:49:27.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:29.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:30.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:30.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:31.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:32.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:33.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:33.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:34.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:36.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:40.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:49:40.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:49:40.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:50:48.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:51.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:50:53.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:42.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:42.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:43.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:44.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:44.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:44.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:45.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:46.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:48.94	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
13:56:48.95	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
13:56:50.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:51.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:52.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:54.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:54.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:56:56.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:59.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:41.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:42.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:43.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:43.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:43.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:44.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:46.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:46.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:57:47.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:49.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:51.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:51.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:52.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:57:54.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:58:18.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:26.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:59:56.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:00:04.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:00:43.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:43.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:44.66	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 25ms.
14:00:47.34	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 25ms.
14:00:51.66	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 15ms.
14:00:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 15ms.
14:00:53.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:53.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:55.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:56.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:35.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:01:42.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:02:34.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:34.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

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14:02:35.04 LSH - - - - Idling
14:02:37.93 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:02:41.61 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:41.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:41.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:42.22 SWS - - - - Idling
14:02:44.50 USH - - - - Idling
14:02:46.00 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:46.01 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:46.62 SWS - - - - Idling
14:02:48.67 USH - - - - Idling
14:02:49.07 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:49.07 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:02:49.87 SWS - - - - Idling
14:02:51.53 USH - - - - Idling
14:02:52.28 LSH - - - - Idling
14:02:58.55 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 200ms.
14:02:58.56 SWS - - 200 200 NIR int.time changed from 15ms to 200ms.
14:03:01.10 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
14:03:02.84 SWS 173.8 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:03:05.32 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:05.33 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:05.35 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:03:11.07 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:03:11.08 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:03:12.10 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:03:50.20 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
14:03:52.68 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:05:01.89 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:05:05.07 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
14:05:06.80 SWS -5.8 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:05:08.63 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:07:06.75 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:07:11.50 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
14:07:18.74 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
14:07:20.51 SWS 173.9 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:07:22.86 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
14:07:25.34 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:07:26.26 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:07:31.19 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:07:33.67 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:07:35.55 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:07:45.99 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:13.73 --- - - - *** cloudy
14:12:36.78 --- - - - *** Cooler temp +1 deg C
14:13:04.99 --- - - - *** NONONO!, +2 deg C!
14:13:13.20 SWS - - - Idling
14:13:13.32 USH - - - Idling
14:13:13.80 LSH - - - Idling
14:13:15.24 --- - - - Reset shutters.
14:13:19.57 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:19.58 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:19.59 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:22.03 SWS - - - Idling
14:13:22.44 USH - - - Idling
14:13:22.69 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
14:13:24.42 SWS -5.8 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:13:24.96 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:24.97 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:27.44 USH - - - Idling
14:13:27.62 SWS - - - Idling
14:13:30.28 LSH - - - Idling
14:13:32.63 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:32.63 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:32.66 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:35.31 USH - - - Idling
14:13:35.51 SWS - - - Idling
14:13:36.51 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
14:13:36.52 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.

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14:13:38.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:39.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:40.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:40.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:42.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:42.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:43.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:13:44.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:44.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:44.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:51.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:13:51.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:13:52.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:14:16.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:16.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:17.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:12.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud patches
14:18:21.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:18:22.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:25.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:18:27.55	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
14:18:27.56	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
14:18:28.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:30.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:18:32.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:12.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:13.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:16.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:17.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:19.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:22.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:33.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:19:35.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:06.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud patches
14:24:58.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:58.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:59.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:59.95	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:25:03.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:03.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:03.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:05.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:06.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:06.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:06.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:07.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:09.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:10.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:10.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:12.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:14.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:16.21	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:25:17.96	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:25:23.58	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
14:25:23.59	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
14:25:28.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:32.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:25:34.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:34.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:34.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:54.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:54.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:54.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:29.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloudy
14:35:04.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:04.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:04.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:09.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:35:09.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:09.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:12.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:12.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:12.78	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:35:14.55	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:35:19.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:20.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:20.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:20.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:21.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:35:26.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:35:32.94	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 45ms.
14:35:32.95	SWS	-	-	-	45	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 45ms.
14:35:38.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:39.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:35:43.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:08.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:08.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:08.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:08.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:09.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:11.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:12.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:12.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:12.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:13.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:15.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:15.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:16.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:18.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:20.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:37:20.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:20.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:20.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:17.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:19.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:20.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:23.08	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:42:25.25	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:42:27.01	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:42:28.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:32.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:36.14	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 300ms.
14:42:36.15	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 45ms to 300ms.
14:42:37.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:41.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:42.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:14.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:44:16.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:44:18.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:44:21.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:44:21.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:44:24.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:44:26.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:27.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:28.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:31.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:44:34.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:38.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:15.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:15.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:16.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:18.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:18.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:18.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:50:21.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:23.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:50:25.09	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:50:27.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:27.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:28.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:29.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:41.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:50:43.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:47.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:50:49.63	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:50:49.64	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:50:51.49	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:50:51.50	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:50:53.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:55.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:50:56.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:09.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:55:37.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloudy
14:55:58.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cooler temp +2 deg C
14:57:50.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:57:57.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:57:59.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:00.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:58:04.04	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:58:04.06	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:58:06.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:07.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:58:08.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:13.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:13.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:14.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:14.58	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:00:18.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:18.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:18.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:19.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:20.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:21.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:21.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:22.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:23.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:24.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:24.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:25.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:27.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:29.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:37.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:37.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:37.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:33.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:33.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:34.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:36.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:36.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:36.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:38.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:39.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:43.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:43.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:44.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:46.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:47.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:47.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:47.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:47.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:31.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** endex
15:15:38.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:15:38.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:39.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:40.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:40.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:40.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:41.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:42.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:50.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:02.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:02.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:02.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:05.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:05.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:05.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:07.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:07.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:07.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:08.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:09.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:17.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.356**.....

 Date **10/4/08**.....

 Operator's name: **A. Wilson**.....

 Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
093000								PREFLIGHT ALL OK. BOTH NEPHS ZEROED. WATER CHILGER TOOK MORE WATER THAN USUAL TODAY. SUSPECT SYSTEM COMPLETELY DRY SO NEEDED MORE FILLING. SEEMS OK.
105100	TRANSIT							System started in transit. Preheater on.
110100	"	FL110	12	4.4	26.9	↘	8	ramping water to +5c.
110954	P1 ↘	R110	1					Start profile 1 ↘
112422	P1		16.5	38.3	33.5	—	6	end P1 @ 500ft. Distinct pollution layer surface to 4000ft.
112517	R1-1	500ft	12.6	29.2	33.7	↗	6	ramping up to 45c. SLR. * Humidity scanning run.
113445	R1-1							End run
113556	R1-2	500ft	12.5	31	90.1	—	44c	Start reciprocal run. Constant Humidity run @ 90%.
115515	R1-2	500ft	12.0	29.5	99.2	↘	45c	ramping down.
120318		"	15.1	29.2	79.8	↘	14	flow speed up to aid drying of the sample wet neph.
122200	"	"	15.2	25.6	34.2	↗	5	rampin up.
123050	"	"	13.6	30.1	89.1	—	44	
123210	"	"	13.6	29.5	91.6	—	44	Just entered a pollution plume.
124120	"	"	16.1	27.9	93.6	↘	44.6	ramp down in quite clear air.
125304	R1-2	500ft.	16.1	30.5	47.5	↘	11.8	end R1-2.
125444	P2	500ft ↗	16	30.1	43.8	↗	10	Start P2 → 4000ft. ramping RH ↗
130750	R2	4000ft	14.4	20	95.8	↘	45	temp set to +40.
131128	R2/P3	4000ft ↘	14.4	16.1	90.1	—	40	end R2 / start P3 to 500ft. Maintaining constant Hum during this profile.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.356**.....

 Date 10/4/08.....

 Operator's name: A. Wilson.....

 Page 2 of 3.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
131816	R3/R3	500ft	14.5	26.6	89.3	-	40.6	end R3/start R3
132215		---	14.5	25.3	89.8	↗	40	Set water temp to 43
132813	R3.1	---	15.2	26.9	95.1	-	43.2	end R3
132929	R4.2	---	16.8 16.8	27.2	95.3	↘	43	ramping down during this reciprocal run.
133836	orbit 1	500ft	16.0	28.5	51.7	↘	13.3	start orbit 1 LH 45° AOB
133954	---							end orbit 1
134027	" 2	---						start orbit 2
134143	" 2							end orbit 2
134253	R3.3	---	14.1	28.8	42	↗	8	Start Southbound Run 3.3. Ramping Humidity up.
134913	R3.3	---	13.9	27.9	86.6	-	44	end Run
135049	R4	500ft ↗	13.8	28.5	90.1	-	44	Start R4 → 4000ft. Constant Humidity during profile.
135640	R4	4000ft	15.6	18.1	94.5	-	44	end R4 @ 4000ft.
135925	orbit 3	4000ft	15.6	14.2	94.5	-	44	start orbit 3 45° AOB Left turn.
140041	" 3	---	15.6	12.2	94.5	-	44	end orbit 3
140114	" 4	---	---	12.9	94.3	-	44	start orbit 4 45° AOB LH
140231	" 4	---	---	13.6	94.7	-	44	end orbit 4.
140309	R4.1	4000ft	---	16.1	94.7	↘	44	Start R4.1. Ramping Humidity down.
141309	---	4000ft	15.7	12.9	44.9	↘	14.1	end R4.1. Good HumidiGRAM during this run. 90% Drop from 95% RH to 50% RH
141449	R4.2 ⁵	FL040	14.6	11.6	38.9	↗	13.6	start R5
142452	R5	FL040	14.5	15.1	92	-	45	end R5. Another good HumidiGRAM.

Flight:

B356

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:	
Heimann:	
Deiced Temp:	
Non-deiced Temp:	

Hygrometers

FWVS:	
Buck CR2:	
General Eastern:	
Johnson Williams:	
Nevzorov:	
Total Water Probe:	

Cameras

Downward Facing:	
Forward Facing:	
Rearward Facing:	
Upward Facing:	

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:	
GIN Applanix:	
INU Honeywell:	
Radar Altimeter:	
RVSM IAS:	
RVSM Static Pressure:	
XR5 GPS:	

Misc Core

AMTG:	
AVAPS:	
Cabin Pressure:	
Fax machine:	
Printer:	
S9 Static Pressure:	
Satcom C:	
Satcom H:	
Turb Centre-Static:	
Turb Left Right:	
Turb Up-Down:	
Turb Horizontal Chk:	
Turb Vertical Chk:	
Weather Radar:	
DLUs:	
DLU AERACK:	
DLU BBR Lower:	
DLU BBR Upper:	
DLU Core Chem:	
DLU Core Consoles:	
DLU Port Aft:	
DLU Port Fwd:	
DLU Stbd Fwd:	

Radiometers

Lower:	
BBR (clear) Lower:	
BBR (IR) Lower:	
BBR (red) Lower:	
Upper:	
BBR (clear) Upper:	
BBR (IR) Upper:	
BBR (red) Upper:	
ARIES:	
DEIMOS:	
IR Camera:	
JNO2 Lower:	
JNO2 Upper:	
JO1D Lower:	
JO1D Upper:	
MARSS:	
SHIMS Lower:	
SHIMS Upper:	
SWS:	
TAFTS:	

Cloud Probes

2DC:	
2DP:	
FFSSP:	
PCASP:	
2DS:	
ADA:	
CAPS:	
CCN:	
CDP:	
CIP 100:	
CIP 25:	
CPI:	
CVI:	
SID1:	
SID2:	

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:	
CPC 3786 H2O:	
Filters 47mm:	
Filters 90mm:	
Neph - Dry:	
Neph - Wet:	
PSAP:	
AMS:	
CPC 3025 (AMS):	
INC:	
VACC:	
CPC 3010A (CVI):	
SP2:	
UHSAS:	

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:	
NOx TE42C:	
Ozone TE49C:	
Ozone TE49:	
SO2 TE43C:	
TDLAS (NIR) CH4:	
TDLAS (NIR) CO2:	
FAGE:	
Formaldehyde:	
NOx FAAM:	
NOxy:	
ORAC:	
PAN:	
PERCA:	
Peroxide:	
PTRMS:	
TDLAS (1C):	
WAS Bags:	
WAS Bottles:	
Misc Non-Core	
CASI/ATM:	
LIDAR:	
LTI:	
SAW Hygrometer:	

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B356

Date: 10 April 2008

Instruments

1. Network – pre-flight, post security, all displays on FM pc locked up including Horace Terminal. Closed all iE windows. Restarted excursion but could not open Terminal Window – “connection timed out”. Rebooted HORACE and pc. No change. Switch NIPS off /on (i.e. power down network), no change. Remove video and Cloud physics Ethernet, no change. Remove AMS connections x 2, then it works! Reconnect AMS, it still works!
2. 2DS – Okay till transit return when flow went negative for a few minutes (in icing conditions). Recovered then okay.
3. CO lamp took till 1230Z to stabilise (on at 0730Z?)

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

1205Z – Connected, received Satpic then disconnected

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 10/4/08

Flight No: B 356

Pre-Flighter: AMW/SC

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	HORACE FACIA SPOKEN!
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☒	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	NOW FITTED
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	FFC CAM A BIT GLIMY
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☒	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	☐			
25	☒	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	MO CAL

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	☒	CGPS	Set up	
29	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	removed
40	☒	All other covers	Removed	
41	☒	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	
	☐			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
	☐	ICEX applied		
	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

50°P

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B356:

Log	Reason
Sortie brief	Not currently available.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
SP2 log	SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Oct 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_104849_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_114849_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_124849_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_134849_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_144849_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_123108_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_104842_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_114842_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_124842_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_134842_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_144842_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_104838_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_114838_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_124838_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_134838_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_144838_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_104846_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_114846_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_124846_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_134846_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080410_r0_b356_144846_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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